

Construction of Chinese Traditional Cultural Nouns Knowledge Base

Ziyang Lin, Xiaoru Wu, Minxuan Feng*, Yi He

Center of Linguistic Big Data and Computational Humanities, School of Literature, Nanjing Normal University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China

linzy.nnu@gmail.com, ephemeral1998@163.com, fennel_2006@163.com, heyi_he@163.com

Abstract: Fine traditional Chinese culture represents the most profound soft power of the Chinese nation. Developing a knowledge base for Chinese traditional cultural nouns is crucial for promoting and preserving this rich heritage within compulsory education effectively. This paper clarifies the definition of traditional cultural terms and selects 3,512 nouns representative of this domain. Utilizing Hownet, we have constructed a categorized thesaurus of Chinese traditional cultural nouns. Furthermore, using CIDOC-CRM as a guideline, we have developed a knowledge base specifically tailored for compulsory education. Subsequent analysis of the system's vocabulary revealed that the number and variety of Chinese traditional cultural nouns students are expected to learn increase progressively with their educational level. This trend aligns with the cognitive development characteristic of each educational phase.

Keywords: Traditional Culture, Cultural Nouns, Classified Thesaurus, Knowledge Base, Compulsory Education

1 Introduction

Fine traditional Chinese culture, embodying the deepest spiritual pursuits of the Chinese nation, boasts a long and unbroken history. It not only stands as a testament to the Chinese nation's unique spiritual identity but also serves as a rich source of nourishment for its development. The appreciation of fine traditional Chinese culture holds profound significance for individuals, society, and the nation at large.

Within the linguistic system, the vocabulary subsystem is particularly vibrant and sensitive, often directly mirroring societal culture. Notably, nouns predominantly carry cultural content. Hence, defining and organizing Chinese traditional cultural nouns offers an intuitive way to understand and appreciate traditional culture.

In recent years, the field of digital humanities has seen significant growth, with data visualization and structuring emerging as prevailing trends. Employing innovative methods to organize and present traditional culture, along with constructing a corresponding traditional cultural noun knowledge base, is crucial for its promotion and preservation.

Our efforts to define traditional cultural terms, organize Chinese traditional cultural nouns in tree and graph structures, and develop a system of semantic categories for Chinese traditional cultural nouns, culminate in the

creation of a traditional cultural noun knowledge base. This initiative not only structures traditional cultural knowledge but also lays a foundational resource for further research endeavors, such as information extraction and semantic analysis.

2 The Definition of Traditional Cultural Words

2.1 Traditional cultural words

To streamline and ensure clarity in the promotion of compulsory education and the popularization of traditional culture, traditional cultural words are defined as words that arose between the epoch of the Three Sovereigns and Five Emperors and to the New Culture Movement of 1919, and the objective reality represented by the concepts are words that denote things, phenomena, behaviors, or ideas of Chinese culture.

2.2.1 Conceptual Meaning

Primarily, our reference sources include dictionaries and Wikipedia entries. Terms whose definitions are intrinsically linked to traditional culture or embody significant traditional cultural elements peculiar to the Chinese nation qualify as traditional cultural words. For example, "quadrangle" is delineated in The Modern Chinese Dictionary as a type of residential architecture featuring houses on all four sides enclosing a central courtyard. Wikipedia further elucidates that its architectural design and spatial arrangement are emblematic of traditional Chinese hierarchical concepts, alongside the principles of Yin Yang and the Five Elements. Such detailed explanations earmark it as a traditional cultural word based on its conceptual meaning.

2.2.2 Time of Creation

Given the varied research lenses and focal points, traditional Chinese culture can be dissected in numerous ways. Considering the overall traits of traditional Chinese culture and its evolutionary trajectory, only terms originating within the timeframe from the epoch of the Three Emperors and Five Emperors to the May Fourth Movement in 1919 are designated as traditional cultural words.

3 Construction of classified thesaurus of Chinese traditional culture

3.1 Review of classified thesaurus

A thesaurus is "a resource in which words with similar meanings are grouped together". [8] Early thesauruses were constructed to serve information retrieval, and the words in the thesaurus tended to be arranged in alphabetical order, with little emphasis on subject overview or systematic display. However, these helped to reveal the intrinsic associations of terms better. [9] Since the 1950s, scholars have tried to apply the classification scheme to the construction of thesauruses. Aitchison developed THE THESAUROFACET, which was compiled by facet analysis, covering scientific, technological, managerial, and other subject. With classification schedules, THE THESAUROFACET promoted the research of the classified thesaurus. [10] There are also many representative thesauruses like UNESCO Thesaurus, Medical Subject Headings (or MESH), Thesaurus of Scientific and Technical Terms, and Information Retrieval Thesaurus of Education Terms, IRTE).

In China, Aeronautical Scientific and Technical Terms Thesaurus was the first classified thesaurus, which conducts in-depth research on the terms of aeronautical science and technology. It is a significant exploration of the development of classified thesaurus. [11] Chinese Classified Thesaurus is one of the most representative classified thesauruses, which draws on the Chinese Library Book Classification, combining classified citation and subject citation. With the help of computer technology, it also makes progress in the processing of conceptual relationships. [12] Since the 1990s, the research of classified thesaurus in China has been gradually transformed from the construction of thesaurus to the ontology, semantic network, and knowledge graphs.

Generally speaking, there are few classified thesauruses studies at home and abroad that are specifically oriented to the culture. Traditional culture is so complex that it needs a classified thesaurus. Among traditional cultural words, nouns can directly reflect the concepts and contents of traditional culture. Therefore, we will construct a classified thesaurus for traditional culture nouns.

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Preparation

The foundational data for this research is sourced from *the National Textbook for Primary and Junior School Education: Fine Traditional Chinese Culture* (hereinafter referred to as the "Textbook"), published by the People's Education Press, and articles from the *China Culture Daily* spanning from 1 July 2011 to 28 July 2021. Utilizing this data, a corpus of approximately 600,000 words was compiled.

To evaluate the effectiveness of tools for segmentation and part of speech tagging, a subset of 1,000 words from this corpus was selected for testing. The testing outcomes revealed that the F1-score for segmentation by Jieba, at 98.5%, surpasses that of HanLP, which stood at 96.3%. This comparison underscores the superior performance of Jieba for the tasks at hand, thereby justifying its selection as the preferred tool for further analysis.

Following the segmentation and part-of-speech tagging processes, a total of 3,512 nouns were identified that align with the previously established definition of traditional cultural words. These nouns were subsequently used to develop a classified thesaurus, systematically organizing the vocabulary in a manner that facilitates both understanding and application. This classified thesaurus not only enriches the lexical resources available for the study of traditional Chinese culture but also supports the educational objectives of integrating these cultural elements into the primary and junior school curriculum, thereby promoting a deeper appreciation and knowledge of China's rich cultural heritage among students.

3.2.2 Using and Adapting Hownet

In constructing the classified thesaurus for traditional culture, it is pivotal to establish a structured system of semantic categories reflective of traditional cultural elements. This endeavor necessitates a detailed examination and categorization of vocabulary not only by thematic relevance but also considering the intricate relationships between terms, particularly in terms of hierarchy. Such an approach ensures that the thesaurus not only serves as a repository of terms but also as a navigable map of the semantic terrain of traditional Chinese culture, highlighting the connections and distinctions among the concepts it comprises.

HowNet is a general knowledge base that reveals the relationships between concepts and the properties possessed by concepts. [13] As the inaugural computable semantic knowledge base, HowNet offers a wealth of semantic knowledge invaluable for applications ranging from lexicography to natural language processing. It accomplishes the depiction of word concepts through the delineation of sememes, which are defined within HowNet as the most fundamental, indivisible units of meaning. Each sememe, of which there are 2,089 identified in HowNet, is categorized into one of seven groups, such as Entity and Event, providing a systematic and unambiguous representation of meanings. The hierarchical organization of sememes within HowNet facilitates a nuanced and precise method for constructing semantic categories for traditional culture, enabling the classified thesaurus to accurately reflect the depth and complexity of traditional Chinese cultural lexicon.

Leveraging HowNet's robust sememe system, the classified thesaurus can thus be developed with a clear

and logical structure that not only categorizes traditional cultural words thematically but also aligns them according to their semantic relationships. This ensures that the thesaurus is both a comprehensive catalog of traditional cultural vocabulary and a dynamic tool that elucidates the semantic web underpinning traditional Chinese culture, offering scholars, educators, and students alike a rich resource for exploring and understanding the vast expanse of China's cultural heritage.

Fig. 1. Hierarchical structure of sememe in HowNet

From Figure 1, it can be seen that the hierarchical structure of sememe in HowNet is not simply a single-level hierarchical structure, but rather a multi-level relationship. Taking the sememes in Entity as examples, "beast|走兽" and "bird|禽" are both at the seventh level of the hierarchical structure of sememes in Entity and are both subordinate to "AnimalHuman|动物".

However, this system is not completely applicable to Chinese traditional cultural nouns. Therefore, this article adds some subordinate sememes. For example, under the sememe "human|人", four labels are added: "true person | 真人", "identity | 身份", "literary character | 文学人物", and "official position | 官职". Under the

sememe "facilities|设施", seven labels are added: "cultural landscape | 文化景观", "defense facilities | 防卫措施", "religious facilities | 宗教设施", "daily buildings | 日常建筑", "transportation facilities | 交通设施", "burial facilities | 墓葬设施", and "technical facilities | 科技设施".

By adding, deleting, and revising the sememe in the system of HowNet, we successfully built a classified thesaurus of 3,512 Chinese traditional cultural nouns.

- 1 {entity|实体}
 - 1.1 {thing|万物}
 - 1.1.1 {physical|物质}
 - 1.1.1.1 {animate|生物}
 - 1.1.1.1.1 {AnimalHuman|动物}
 - 1.1.1.1.1.1 {human|人}
 - 真人
 - 身份
 - 文学人物
 - 官职
 - 1.1.1.1.1.1.1 {humanized|拟人}
 - 1.1.1.1.1.2 {animal|兽}
 - 1.1.1.1.1.2.1 {beast|走兽}
 - 1.1.1.1.1.2.2 {livestock|牲畜}
 - 1.1.1.1.1.2.3 {bird|禽}
 - 1.1.1.1.1.2.4 {InsectWorm|虫}

Fig. 2. Structure of sememe system of Chinese traditional cultural nouns

4 Construction of Chinese traditional cultural nouns knowledge base

Knowledge base, also called knowledge warehouse, is the product of combining traditional database and artificial intelligence technology. [14] While databases emphasize data storage, knowledge bases focus more on the organization, management, and representation of data. [15] The method of constructing a knowledge base based on ontology is more common, and scholars have tried to apply it to the cultural field. [16] The construction of Chinese traditional cultural nouns knowledge base is also mainly based on ontology.

Ontology is the study of how human knowledge system is represented and organized. [17] It is usually a triple containing knowledge, concepts, and relationships. Therefore, there are two points to be clarified when constructing a knowledge base based on ontology. The first is what kinds of knowledge are required. The second is what concepts the knowledge is subordinate to and how the relationships between the concepts are represented.

4.1 Knowledge base of Chinese traditional cultural nouns

The Knowledge Base of Chinese Traditional Cultural Nouns mainly consists of 3,512 traditional cultural nouns. These nouns are categorized into 86 classes, of which only 12 classes have been processed. The total number of nouns in these 12 classes accounts for 80% of all nouns, thereby providing a representative sample.

Fig. 3. Overview of Knowledge base of Chinese traditional cultural nouns

To build a knowledge base of Chinese traditional cultural nouns based on ontology, it is necessary to find a way to represent the knowledge of Chinese traditional cultural nouns. And this knowledge is usually presented in the conceptual meanings of words, so we need to sort out the conceptual meanings of Chinese traditional cultural nouns.

Taking the nouns in {human | 人} as an example, their conceptual meanings are annotated as follows:

Table 1. Example of conceptual meaning annotation of nouns in {human | 人}

Labels	Example of Annotation
/生卒/(birth & death)	王献之/称谓/(344-386), /生卒/东晋/朝代/书法家。/身份/字子敬, /称谓/琅邪临沂(今属山东)人。/出生地/各体皆精, 行草尤佳, 号“破体”, 富豪迈之气, 对后世影响很大。/评价/有墨迹《鸭头丸
/朝代/(dynasty)	
/出生地/(birthplace)	

/身份/(identity)	帖》等存世。 /成果/ 逸事多见于《世说新语》与《晋书·王羲之传》 中。 /参见文献/
/地位/(status)	
/称谓/(alternative names)	
/事件/(events)	
/评价/(appraisals)	
/成果/(achievements)	
/参见文献/(references)	

4.2 Concepts and their Relationships

On this basis, we use the Conceptual Reference Model (CRM) proposed by the International Committee for Documentation (CIDOC) to represent the conceptual and inter-conceptual relationships of the knowledge of Chinese traditional cultural nouns. CRM is a knowledge ontology that facilitates the integration, transfer, and mutual exchange of diverse cultural heritage information sources. CIDOC-CRM (ISO/CD21127) has been accepted as the international standard for CRM for cultural assets museums consulting on cultural objects by ISOTC46/SC4 and is widely used.

In CRM, concepts are known as "Classes" and relationships are known as "Properties". CRM 7.2.1 defines 81 Classes and 148 Properties. The high-level categories are mainly Temporal_Entity, Time-Span, Place, Dimension, and Persistent_Item. Take the class Event as an example, the following will illustrate the way CIDOC-CRM describes classes and the property relationships between them.

Fig. 4. CIDOC-CRM description of Event classes and property relationships

The class Event needs the class Actor, so the property relationship between them is "participated in". Similarly, the property relationship between the class Event and the class Time-span is "take place within".

4.3 Mapping

Next, the mapping of knowledge of Chinese traditional cultural nouns to classes in CIDOC-CRM is required.

In CIDOC-CRM, the class that directly describes characters is *E21_Person*, which includes both real persons and fictional character images. So we classified all the words under *{human | 人}* in thesaurus into *E21_Person*. The classes describing birth and death in CRM are *E67_Birth* and *E69_Death*, which refer to the birth and death of any living thing respectively. Therefore the label */生卒/* (birth & death) can be mapped to these two classes. The dynasty in which a person lives is a time-span concept that corresponds to the *E52_Time-Span* in CRM, so the label */朝代/* (dynasty) can be mapped to this class. By analogy, the label */出生地/* (birthplace) can be mapped to *E53_Place*, */称谓/* (Alternative Names) can be mapped to *E41_Appellation*, */事件/* (Events) can be mapped to *E5_Event*, */身份/* (Identity) can be mapped to *E55_Type*, and */成果/* (Achievements) can be mapped to *E28_Conceptual Object*. Finally, we get the correspondence between annotations of conceptual meanings of and classes in CIDOC-CRM.

Table 2. The mapping of knowledge of Chinese traditional cultural nouns and classes in CIDOC-CRM

Knowledge of Chinese traditional cultural nouns	Classes in CIDOC-CRM
/人物/{human 人}	E21_Person
/生卒/(birth & death)	E67_Birth/E69_Death
/出生地/(birthplace)	E53_Place
/身份/(identity)	E55_Type
/地位/(status)	E62_String
/称谓/(alternative names)	E41_Appellation
/事件/(events)	E5_Event
/评价/(appraisals)	E62_String
/成果/(achievements)	E28_Conceptual Object
/参见文献/(references)	E31_Document
/朝代/(dynasty)	E52_Time-Span

However, some labels could not correspond to the classes in CIDOC-CRM, so 8 new classes were added, starting with T, to distinguish them from the established classes. The CIDOC-CRM class hierarchy table of 12 categories of nouns is shown below. The "-" in front of a class is used to indicate its hierarchy." The fewer the number of "-", the higher the level is, and the more abstract the concept is.

Table 3. CIDOC-CRM class hierarchy of 12 categories of nouns

E1 -CRM Entity
E2 -Temporal Entity
E3 --Condition State
E4 --Period
E5 ---Event
E13 ----Attribute Assignment
E14 ----- Condition Assessment
E65 -----Creation
E63 ---- Beginning of Existence
E67 ----- Birth

E64 - - - - End of Existence
E69 - - - - -Death
E77-Persistent Item
E70 - - -Thing
E72 - - -Legal Object
E18 - - - -Physical Thing
.....
T1 -Manner
T2 -Reference
T3 -Example
T4 -Assertion
T5 -Qualitative
T6 -Style
T7 -Origin

At this point, the classes can be connected through the properties in CIDOC-CRM. The property relationships between classes are shown in the following table:

Table 4. Property relationships between classes

Classes as sources	Property	Classes as goals
E21_Person	P98_brought into life (was born)	E67_Birth
E21_Person	P100_was death of (died in)	E69_Death
E39_Actor	P11_had participant (participated in)	E5_Event
E41_Appellation	P1_is identified by (identifies)	E1_Entity
E53_Place	P74_has current or former residence	E39_Actor

	(is the current or former residence of)	
E52_Time-Span	P4_has timespan (is timespan of)	E2_Temporal Entity
E62_String	P3_has note	E1_Entity
E55_Type	P42_assigned (was assigned by)	E39_Actor
.....

4.4 Using protégé

Once we have clarified the content of the ontology of Chinese traditional cultural nouns, we can construct an ontology model of the traditional culture knowledge base in protégé software.

4.4.1 Add classes

Fig. 5. Classes in protégé

4.4.2 Add properties

Fig. 6. Properties in protégé

In OWL language, there are two types of properties. One is called Object Properties, which represents a relationship between individuals. There is also a type called Datatype Properties, which represents the relationship between individuals and values, such as age and height. Generally speaking, Object properties are more common.

4.4.3 Instantiation

Instantiation is the most critical step in implementing a knowledge base. When a large number of instances are given corresponding properties and property values, a knowledge base in the relevant field is formed. The creation of an instance mainly consists of two steps: first, select a class create an instance of that class, and then fill in the values of each slot of the instance.

There is an OntoGraf function in protégé. Using it, not only can you visualize the constructed classes and properties, but when you have expanded enough instances you can present the instances under the whole ontology as a knowledge graph. And you can also choose to view them in different views, which makes it easier to see the relationship between different entities and entities, and different nouns and nouns. This is shown in the figure below:

Fig. 7. Instantiation of protégé of Chinese traditional cultural nouns

5 Application of Knowledge Base

5.1 Primarily serving compulsory education

A total of 1385 Chinese traditional cultural nouns related to compulsory education were extracted from the knowledge base, covering 59 categories. After categorizing them by educational level into low primary (grades 1-2), mid primary (grades 3-4), high primary (grades 5-6), and junior high school (grades 7-9), it was found that the number of Chinese traditional cultural nouns increases from low primary to junior high school in general.

Fig. 8. Number of words for Chinese traditional cultural nouns in compulsory education

Some of the categories were extracted from the knowledge base to observe their distribution across the stages of compulsory education, as shown in the figure:

Fig. 9. Distribution of categories of Chinese traditional cultural nouns in compulsory education

The "character|文字" in the image above is only distributed in grades 1-2, and there are only three words in the category: "pictographs", "associative compounds", and "pictophonetic". Literacy is the basic requirement for reading, and learners in the compulsory education stage, only need to understand the relevant knowledge of the text at the beginning of learning.

In the image above, the two categories of "clothing|衣物" and "facilities|设施" show an increasing number of internal words and learning difficulty as grades increase. Taking "clothing|衣物" as an example, students in grades 3-4 only need to master words such as "belt" and "crown", while students in grades 5-6 need to master more complex words such as "Ru Skirt" and "cross collar". According to prototype theory, the words learned during primary school are often at the basic level categories, and even if they are not at the basic level categories, the integrity of the words is relatively high and easy to understand. However, the words learned during junior high school are mostly located in subordinate categories, such as "wooden clogs", "coronation robes", "funeral clothes", etc. Correct understanding and application of these words require students to have a higher level of cognition.

While "money|货币" and "system|制度" are only distributed in the upper grades of primary schools and

junior high schools, as the vocabulary within these categories is often associated with specific economic and political phenomena, and the requirements for learners are relatively high.

To sum up, the system as a whole matches the learning abilities and cognitive characteristics of students in the compulsory education stage. As they grow older, learners need to master more Chinese traditional cultural nouns, which is more difficult and involves much more culture and phenomena.

5.2 Serving the popularization for the general public

Further analysis of the terms in the compulsory education stage from both *China Culture Daily* and *Textbook* revealed a total of 1989 words, of which 630 were only found in *China Culture Daily*, 1176 were only found in *Textbook*, and 183 were found in both *China Culture Daily* and *Textbook*. There were a total of 91 categories, of which 48 were only found in *China Culture Daily*, 8 were only found in *Textbook*, and 35 were found in both *China Culture Daily* and *Textbook*. The distribution of categories is shown in the following figure:

Fig. 10. Sememe only in *Textbook*

Fig. 11. Sememe only in *China Culture Daily*

In terms of the unique categories covered by *China Culture Daily* and *Textbook*, the former contains a broader range of unique categories, including technology, nature, emotions, objects, animals, art, and skills, while the latter contains relatively fewer unique categories, mostly including words such as objects. It can be seen that the cultural knowledge involved in cultural words is more extensive, focusing on various aspects of public life, and paying attention to more professional scientific interpretation of a certain thing. The entries in the *Textbook* are more humanistic, coming from classic texts and humanistic allusions, indicating that school education pays more attention to the inheritance and development of classical culture. The knowledge base constructed based on these two corpora can be used for both compulsory education and popularization.

6 Conclusion

Firstly, the definition of traditional cultural words needs to be further improved. Even though many restrictions have been added to the definition, there may still be ambiguity in the specific practice process, which needs to be supplemented and revised in time.

Secondly, the knowledge base is relatively small and needs to be expanded.

Thirdly, although the entity and property categories have been adjusted multiple times during the construction of the ontology model, the number of instantiations is insufficient.

In the future, we will continue to improve the Chinese traditional cultural nouns knowledge base. First, we will improve the annotation and definition system to make the knowledge base serve the era in the long-term context. Second, we will combine the leveling research and learning word list [18] and other related theories to

make the Chinese traditional cultural nouns knowledge base better serve the young students in different learning stages. Finally, there are still a large number of Chinese traditional cultural nouns that can be instantiated. In the future, they can be formally expressed to construct online databases or learning platforms.

References

- [1] Nida, E.: *Linguistics and Ethnology in Translation-Problems*. WORD. 1(2), 194-208(1945).
- [2] Nida, E.: *Toward a Science of Translating*. Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press, Shanghai (2004).
- [3] Eastman, C.: "Culture-Loaded" Vocabulary and Language Resurrect. *Current Anthropology*, 20(2), 401-402(1979).
- [4] Newmark, P.: *A Textbook of Translation*. Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press, Shanghai (2001).
- [5] Chang, J.: *Chinese Vocabulary and Culture*. Peking University Press, Beijing (1995). (In Chinese)
- [6] Li, X.: *Research on Cultural Teaching of Chinese as a Second Language*. The Commercial Press, Beijing (2007). (In Chinese)
- [7] Chen, L.: The translation of the culture-specific words. *J. Chongqing Vocational & Technical Institute*. 15(03), 113–115 (2006). (In Chinese)
- [8] Kilgarriff, A., & Yallop, C. What's in a Thesaurus? *LREC*, 1371-1379(2000)
- [9] Aitchison, J.: THE THESAUROFACET: A Multipurpose Retrieval Language Tool. *Journal of Documentation*, 26(3), 187–203(1970). <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb026493>
- [10] Aitchison, J. & Clarke, S.: The Thesaurus: A Historical Viewpoint, with a Look to the Future. *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly*. 37(3-4), 5–21(2004). https://doi.org/10.1300/j104v37n03_02
- [11] No.628 Research Institute of the Third Ministry of Machinery Industry.: *Aeronautical Scientific and Technical Terms Thesaurus*. No. 628 Research Institute of the Third Ministry of Machinery Industry, Beijing (1965). (In Chinese)
- [12] Bu, S. & Wang, D.: Chinese Classified Thesaurus and its Development and Application in the Internet Era. *Library and Information Service*, 49(7), 25-28+75(2005). (In Chinese)
- [13] Dong, Z., & Dong, Q.: HowNet - a hybrid language and knowledge resource. *International Conference on Natural Language Processing and Knowledge Engineering*, 820-824(2003).
- [14] Yuan, L., Zhang, H., Chen, J. & Lu, J.: Design Pattern of Knowledge Base Based on Ontology Knowledge Model. *Computer Engineering and Applications*. 30, 65-68+104(2006). (In Chinese)
- [15] Hamid, R., David, M., Lakshmi, S. & Richard, T.: Knowledge warehouse: an architectural integration of knowledge management, decision support, artificial intelligence and data warehousing. *Decision Support System*, 33(2), 143-161(2002).
- [16] Wei, Q. & Liu, M.: Construction of Knowledge Base of Intangible Cultural Heritage. *Research On Library Science*, 6, 33-38(2020). DOI:10.15941/j.cnki.issn1001-0424.2020.06.005. (In Chinese)

- [17] Yan, L. & Chu, H.: Extracting Concepts and Semantic Associates for Teaching Tang 300 Poems to L2 Learners. *Chinese Lexical Semantics. CLSW 2022. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 13495. Springer, Cham(2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-28953-8_18
- [18] Su, X.: Theory and Method in Compiling List of Common Words in Compulsory Education (Draft). *Applied Linguistics*. 3, 2-11(2017). DOI:10.16499/j.cnki.1003-5397.2017.03.001. (In Chinese) Aitchison, J.: THE THESAUROFACET: A Multipurpose Retrieval Language Tool. *Journal of Documentation*, **26**(3), 187–203(1970). <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb026493>